

Platform-driven English Language Learning: A Review of the Literature

Zeineb Ayachi

Affiliation: Higher School of Digital Economy of Manouba - Tunisia/ Laboratoire
Transcrit Paris 8

Abstract

This work presents a literature review of papers spanning from January 2020 to May 2024, and which study the preferred learning strategies and adopted platforms the English learners use in their autonomous learning journey. An exploration of whether the learners employ certain strategies with certain platforms and whether the challenges were platform-related was also implemented. Results from the descriptive data indicate a growing research interest in autonomous English learning in 2024. The main adopted methodology was the quantitative one allowing for replication to further examine the results. Results pertaining to the research questions revealed different strategies, including self-regulated strategies as the most adopted one the online learners use. The online learners also used different platforms like e-learning, digital gaming, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Social Networking Sites (SNS), virtual reality (VR), and videos. With regards to whether the strategies and the challenges were platform-related, the results showed that neither the strategies nor the challenges were platform-related. The learners use different strategies depending on the activities offered by the platform they are employing; the challenges, on the other hand, were common to almost all the platforms with technical and psychological challenges emerging as the most common issues. The current literature review provides researchers with guidance for future studies in terms of key words and manuscripts' selection.

Keywords: English learning, Strategies, Platforms, Challenges, Literature Review

Introduction

The internet has significantly changed the way people all over the world live (Wellman & Haythornthwaite, 2002), communicate (Hampton et al., 2010), work (Wallace, 2004), and learn (Singh et al, 2023). Such a revolution has empowered people (Christos & Joo, 2021) and gave them more autonomy and flexibility in choosing what, how, and when to act and not act as global netizens in this global public space based on their needs and interests (Yue et al., 2020). As an individual trait but also as an outcome of environmental factors (Little, 1991), autonomous working (Athanasiadou & Theriou, 2021) and learning (Maatuk et al, 2022) have gained ground with the lockdown imposed by the outbreak of the Covid 19. It is in this context of lockdown, evolving digital tools and platforms that learning a language such as English has

seen a significant shift allowing learners to achieve their language learning goals in ways that were not conceivable before (Yousefi, 2014).

With the increasing availability of online resources, besides mastering traditional literacy skills, learners are required to apply certain digital skills and strategies; including the ability to understand, assess, combine, apply, and generate knowledge in order to thrive as learners and future professionals in this evolutionary environment (Wei, 2023). The study of English learning in the digital age is gaining more attention and scope, making the learners at the center of the learning process thanks to the vast opportunities and tools this digital transformation is offering (Dash, 2022). Studying the evolution of learning English in the digital era provides an important understanding that will help update teaching practices and improve learning outcomes.

This research consists of a literature review (LR) of four years of research involving papers published during and post Covid-19 period; from 2020 to 2024 studying the evolution of independent English learning during the digital area that focused more on an autonomous lifestyle due to social distancing imposed by Covid-19 (Bajaj et al., 2020). Addressing autonomous English learners' strategies and the challenges they face in their learning journey is important to different stakeholders; including course providers and platform developers, given that the key goal of online platforms is to provide an added value to autonomous learning and offer the learners meaningful experiences with the learning content. In this regard, the current work aims to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the main learning strategies for autonomous learners of English?
2. What are the main learning platforms?
3. Are the strategies platform-related?
4. Are the challenges platform-related?

The remainder of this paper is structured as follows: section two presents related works on the evolution of the internet as a digital learning space, focusing on the learners' behaviors and challenges. Section three is dedicated to explaining the methodology, and section four displays the main results and provides the reader with a structured discussion based on the important trends revealed by this LR. Finally, the conclusion section points to the study limitations and suggests orientations for future research.

Related works

Navigating the internet and benefitting from the plethora of opportunities it offers in several fields has required being familiar with some important concepts that are seemingly intertwined. As the focus here is on learning, such concepts involve digital transformation, digital literacy, and digital learning, among others.

Digital transformation is defined as “a process that aims to improve an entity by triggering significant changes to its properties through combinations of information, computing, communication, and connectivity technologies” (Vial, 2019, p:1). This shift has brought about

a new type of skills; namely digital literacy, enabling individuals to make sense of the learning content and thrive in the new environment (Westerman et al., 2014).

Digital literacy involves mastering hardware and software skills (Shelly et al., 2018), analytical skills (Grolemond & Wickham, 2016), development skills (Martin, 2008), and interaction with digital content (Rheingold, 2014). Digital literacy allows individuals to appropriately access learning databases, make sense of the large amount of information and do research (Jaeger & Bertot, 2013). Digital literacy skills are essential for efficient participation in digital learning environments (Hsieh, 2017) enabling learners to browse digital learning platforms, have access to online educational resources, and effectively use digital tools for learning goals (Belshaw, 2012).

Digital learning, also known as online learning, distance learning, web-based learning or e-learning involves the use of digital technologies to provide academic content and promote learning (Wheeler, 2012). In this sense, an awareness of available learning platforms, pedagogical practices implemented, the evaluation process, learners' online strategies, and challenges they meet become necessary in rethinking the learning process of an English learner in this complex environment.

Online learners' strategies

For Oxford (2003), "strategies are among the main factors that help determine how—and how well—our students learn a second or foreign language" (p. 1). Although the goal of a learner learning English whether in-person classes or online is to be autonomous in their learning journey and master the language, the strategies differ according to the environment. While in-person, strategies range from cognitive, memory, compensation, as direct strategies, and from metacognitive, affective, and social strategies (Oxford, 1999), online learners build on these strategies due to the unique characteristics of the online environment; including its dependence on technology, asynchronous interactions, and limited social connections (Anderson, 2003).

Learning online involves different strategies that make it possible for the learners to meet their learning goals. Such strategies include self-paced learning, whereby learners learn at their own pace, review materials according to their needs, and achieve their learning goals according to their schedules (Garrison & Vaughan, 2008). Online learners are also likely to develop peer learning and collaboration (Mokwa-Tarnowska, 2020) through discussion forums, virtual group interactions (Rabbany et al., 2014), and language exchange opportunities that enable them to improve their English language skills (Mohamed et al., 2020) and promote their intercultural competence that would be lacking in traditional learning environments (O'Dowd, 2011). Self-regulated learning is another strategy that online learners use to monitor their learning (Zimmerman, 2002). Besides, in contrast to traditional classroom environments, online learners often feel responsible for their learning in the absence of real-time supervision from instructors, which requires a higher level of self-regulation to stay motivated and on track during their learning journey (Cheng, 2011). This is carried through goal setting, time management, and knowledge assessment through the use of a set of digital tools (Selvi & Panneerselvam, 2012). Last but not least, online learning involves self-directed strategies which fosters autonomy and the ability to self-monitor the whole learning experience (Song &

Hill, 2007). Similar to self-regulated learning, self-directed strategy also involves being responsible for one's own learning through setting goals, identifying learning needs, finding resources, and evaluating the learning progress (Mentz & Lubbe, 2021).

Online learning platforms

The internet has provided a digital space that has revolutionized learning whereby access to and retention of information has been made easy (Hsu, 2007) leading thereby to more interactive learning, easier knowledge sharing, and increased motivation to learn through engaging and innovative approaches to education (Lacka & Wong, 2021). From virtual learning environments to language learning apps, free educational resources are offered to the learners allowing them to access learning resources at their convenience anywhere and anytime (Haleem et al, 2022). For example, some platforms might prioritize interactive tasks and multimedia content, while others might emphasize synchronous classes and peer collaboration (Halim & Sunarti, 2021). In this context, digital gaming has become one main learning platform for English learners due to several key factors. In fact, besides the fact that playing “is a natural process of learning whereby children develop physically, cognitively, emotionally, and socially through problem-solving and perseverance” (Reinders, 2016, p. 2), digital gaming increases student engagement and motivation leading thereby to improved language learning (Li, et al, 2022). Social Networking Sites seem to facilitate interaction with other learners and teachers and enhance conversational skills (Yunita et al, 2022). Artificial intelligence has also gained popularity among English learners through personalized experiences and immediate feedback (Tiwari, 2024). Furthermore, AI - powered chatbots and virtual tutors provide interactive and engaging environments for students to improve their language skills, fostering active participation and self -directed learning (Lashari & Umrani, 2023).

Learners' online learning challenges

Despite all the benefits the digital space offers for the learners, the latter still face various challenges when engaging in online learning. Among the most notable challenges that learners have reported are technical issues, including slow internet speed (Coman et al., 2020), software incompatibility, and hardware breakdown (Tondeur et al., 2017). Other obstacles have been reported relating to the learner per se. These include lack of motivation due to distractions at home, absence of face-to-face interactions, or solitude (Al Lily et al., 2019; Yusuf & Al-Banawi, 2013). Besides, despite the flexibility the digital space provides, the learner may sometimes have difficulty managing their time and focus while learning for a longer period of time online (Amir et al., 2020). Another element, mainly pedagogical, that might be considered challenging for the online learner is the inability to understand the learning content in the absence of a human instructor (Bernard et al., 2009).

Addressing the learners' online learning experience is important for stakeholders. A systematic review of the literature during and post Covid-19 (2020-2024) whereby autonomous learning was fostered during periods of isolation, loneliness, and uncertainty imposed by the Covid-19

(Bec et al., 2021). Such a review would shed light on this learning experience and explore the main findings that would be of benefit to different stakeholders; including the learners, instructors, and course delivery providers.

Methodology

This work aims to provide a comprehensive review of papers studying online English language learning during and post Covid-19 and related concepts, including online learning platforms, online learner strategies, and challenges met by the learners. To this end, this study provides a Literature Review (LR) of research articles published between January 2014 and May 2024 that studied online English language learning while focusing on the learners' autonomous learning. The search method for this analysis was conducted in two phases: (1) a search by keywords and similar combinations of keywords to obtain articles from January 2014 to May 2024 dealing with online English language learning; and (2) a content analysis, which in addition to identifying the main concept under study and its related notions, explored the relationship between them. The two stages are explained below.

Keywords-based search

Keywords-based research was carried out to obtain articles dealing with online English language learning from January 2014 up to May 2024. To this end, relevant papers in English were collected from Google Scholar and ScienceDirect databases based on a search with the key terms; namely, autonomous English language learning, the digital age, strategies, and challenges, and using “review articles” and “research articles” as filters.

This stage enabled the selection of 1817 papers, including 980 results from Google Scholar and 837 papers from ScienceDirect. Subsequently, a floating reading was carried out. It consisted of reading titles, keywords and abstracts of the retained papers and checking if these papers provide insight regarding the relationship between the four key terms aforementioned. This step enabled the selection of 23 papers.

Content analysis

In line with Erlingsson and Brysiewicz (2017), both quantitative and qualitative content analysis was used in the current literature review. Content analysis was carried out as follows: first, the retained papers were read going through titles, keywords, abstracts, and body texts; second, the units and categories of analysis were defined; third, coding rules were developed, whereby data were coded for reference. Finally, the results were analyzed and conclusions were drawn. The above-mentioned steps were implemented as follows: after reading the data, units and categories of analysis were defined by classifying the papers by order number, publisher, year, and context. A descriptive analysis was carried to explore the growing trend of publications, as well as the methodologies used. Then an analysis of each of the research questions was carried out. To answer each of the research questions, a classification scheme

was implemented. For example, for research question 1: what are the main learning strategies for autonomous learners of English? the learners' learning approaches were classified into four main sets of strategies based on the literature. For research questions two: what are the main learning platforms? the platforms were classified into six main platforms. Finally, to answer research question three - Are English learning strategies platform-dependent? - and research question four - are the challenges the English learners face platform-dependent? the strategies and the challenges were spotted in relation to each of the platforms. The final step presented an overview of the main results. Conclusions were then drawn, and orientations for future research were suggested.

Results and discussion

This section presents data pertaining to the published papers revealed through the descriptive analysis; including paper publication trends over 2020-2024 and related methodologies. It also displays an analysis related to the four research questions; namely the main strategies and platforms used, as well as any relationship between the platforms and specific strategies, and the platforms and any particular challenges.

Descriptive analysis

Remarkable number of papers in 2024

Despite the short period January 2020-May 2024, paper publication indicates a significant increase (15 papers) in 2024 relating to autonomous English learning, strategies and challenges as shown in Figure 1. This is due to several key reasons. First, the shift towards distance and hybrid learning stimulated by the COVID-19 pandemic has made it necessary for students to be more autonomous in their learning leading to several studies investigating successful strategies promoting autonomy in English language learners (Al Ghazali, 2020; Ariebowo, 2021; Sato et al., 2024). Second, the concept of autonomous learning has gained remarkable significance as teachers and researchers acknowledge its capacity to boost learners' motivation and outcomes (Acosta, 2024; Khusnul et al., 2019). Third, the fast development trend of educational technologies has offered novel tools and platforms to support autonomous learning (Haleem et al., 2022).

Paper publication evolution

Figure 1: Paper publication evolution

Methodologies used

The main methodologies used in the studied papers (23) included quantitative, qualitative, mixed, and review. The quantitative methodology takes the lead as it was adopted in 8 papers (Zarrati et al, 2024; Nazari et al, 2021; Kic-Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2024; Teng & Wu, 2024; Abdallah & Alshaye, 2024; Meng et al., 2023; Le et al., 2024; Mihai et al., 2022). The quantitative method requires the use and analysis of numerical data techniques to answer questions like who, how much, what, where, when, how many, and how (Williams, 2011). Quantitative research is often used in humanities as it provides objective data that can be statistically analyzed, offering clear and unbiased results that can validate or refute initial hypotheses (Ghanad, 2023). The quantitative methodology also facilitates comparative analysis across diverse groups or time periods, allowing researchers to spot patterns and correlations (Apuke, 2017). Such comparative studies are often necessary in the humanities to understand the characteristics of certain individuals, groups, or situations (Ghanad, 2023). Last but not least, quantitative research allows for generalizations to larger populations (Apuke, 2017), and replications boosting the reliability and credibility of the research findings, contributing thereby to building a strong knowledge base in the humanities (Lemercier & Zalc, 2019).

The review method follows with 6 papers (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023; Chauncey & McKenna, 2023; Acquah & Katz, 2020; Su et al., 2024; Buddha et al., 2024; Sözlér, 2024). The review method communicates complex concepts by synthesizing existing research findings and uncovering relevant areas in research (Snyder, 2019).

The mixed method involving both the quantitative and the qualitative research design to provide a more comprehensive understanding of the research issue (Timans et al., 2019) was used in 5 papers (Chowdhury et al., 2024; Khafaga & Al-Johani, 2024; Nguyen, 2024; Malik & Qureshi, 2024; Kim & Kim, 2024).

Finally, the qualitative method was used in 4 papers (Teng, 2024; Ericsson & Johannsson, 2023; Jabarali, et al., 2024; Li, 2020). Qualitative research, thanks to its deep exploration of complex issues, offers a richer understanding of human existence by looking into the complexity of culture, society, and individual lives (Gautam & Gautam, 2023).

Research questions analysis

Main learners' strategies

Table 1 presents the main strategies used as well as the frequency of their occurrence. Note that the same article can sometimes include more than one strategy. The strategies used were classified on a clustering basis, including self-regulated strategies, self-directed strategies, self-paced strategies, peer learning and collaboration, and other strategies. As can be seen in Table 1, the main strategies depicted in the articles revolved around the self-regulated learning strategies ($f=10$) (Acquah & Katz, 2020; Chauncey & McKenna, 2023; Chowdhury et al, 2024; Kic-Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2020; Khafaga & Al-Johani, 2024; Meng et al., 2023; Nazari et al., 2021; Teng, 2024; Teng & Wu, 2024; Zhai & Wibowo, 2023). Self-regulated related strategies ranged from metacognitive, self-efficacy to meaning negotiation. Self-regulated strategies seem to be mostly used by online learners as in line with (Cheng, 2011), learners online feel responsible for their learning due to the lack of monitoring from teachers as would be the case in traditional classroom environments. Next comes the self-directed learning ($f=7$) (Ayesha & Qureshi, 2024; Buddha et al., 2024; Jabarali et al., 2024; Le et al., 2024; Mihai et al., 2021; Sözlür, 2024; Zarrati et al, 2024) which is mostly used in reading, writing, and grammar tasks. This is in agreement with Mentz and Lubbe (2021), who suggest that like self-regulated, self-directed learning is one important strategy that makes the online learner set goals, identify learning needs, find resources, and evaluate the learning progress to reach their learning objective. Peer learning and collaboration strategies (Buddha et al., 2024; Kim & Kim, 2024; Le et al., 2024; Zhai & Wibowo, 2023; Ericsson & Johannsson, 2023; Su et al., 2024; Nguyen, 2024) including interaction opportunities, relational strategies, collaborative peer reviews and feedback, connections, are equally cited ($f=7$). Finally, self-paced learning strategies ($f=1$) (Abdallah & Alshaye, 2024) and multimodal literacies ($f=1$) (Li, 2020) were depicted as the least used strategies in the articles.

Table 1

Main learning strategies

Type of learning strategies	example of strategies/implementation areas	Frequency
Self-regulated learning strategies	Metacognitive, control, goal-orientation, language learning motivation, self-efficacy belief, using context clues to understand new vocabulary or concepts, metacognitive reasoning strategies, contextual recognition strategies, categorization strategy, critical thinking, cognitive flexibility, awareness, negotiation for meaning strategies	10
Self-directed learning strategies	reading and writing tasks, grammar exercises	7
peer learning and collaboration	Interaction opportunities, relational strategies, collaborative peer reviews and feedback, connections	7
Self-paced learning strategies	Flipped classroom	1
Others	Multimodal literacies	1

Main learning platforms

Figure 2 presents the main learning platforms. As can be seen, digital games are the leading learning platforms for English learning ($F= 7$) (Acquah & Katz, 2020; Buddha et al., 2024; Chowdhury et al., 2024; Teng, 2024; Zarrati et al., 2024; Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2024; Sözlür, 2024). This seems to agree with Reinders (2016) and Lashari and Umrani (2023) who support the use of online gaming for language learners as it improves language learning thanks to the natural environment it provides besides the engagement and the motivation the learners feel during the game.

Gaming based learning is followed by e-learning platforms ($f= 6$) (Jabarali et al., 2024; Kim & Kim, 2024; Li, 2020; Meng et al., 2023; Mihai et al., 2024; Teng & Wu, 2024). E-learning platforms remain popular among English learners due to their flexibility enabling them to access a large number of learning materials (Haleem et al., 2022), their cost effectiveness (Bennani et al., 2022), as well as promoting peer learning and information exchange through virtual discussions, peer interactions, and group projects (Laranjeiro, 2022).

AI learning platforms rank third ($F= 4$) (Chauncey & McKenna, 2023; Ericsson & Johansson, 2023; Nazari et al., 2021; Zhai & Wibowo, 2023). Despite the personalized experience and immediate feedback AI platforms offer English language learners (Tiwari, 2024), they seem to be in their infancy. This may be explained by the novelty of the technology (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023).

Social networking sites rank fourth ($F= 3$) (Budha et al.; 2024; Le et al.; 2024; Malik & Qureshi, 2024). These platforms provide opportunities to interact with native speakers and other learners which boosts performance (Almarwaey, 2017).

Finally, virtual learning environments (Su et al, 2024; Khafaga & Maneh Al-Johani, 2024), and videos were equally cited (Abdallah & Alshaye, 2024; Nguyen, 2024) ($f=2$), respectively. The low frequency of the use of these platforms can be explained by some challenges that will be presented subsequently.

Main learning platforms

Figure 2: Main learning platforms

Strategies and platforms

Figure 3 presents a synthesis of the main platforms and the strategies used for each. Following the clustering basis of the learners' strategies (Table 1), the strategies include self-regulated,

self-directed, self-paced, peer learning and collaboration, and others like multimodal literacies. As can be seen, the learners can use the same learning strategies with different platforms depending on whether the platform per se emphasizes interactive and multimedia content or synchronous learning and peer collaboration (Halim & Sunarti, 2021). According to Figure 3 there are some strategies that seem to be used mostly with specific platforms. The use of specific strategies is presented by order of frequency. Peer learning seems to be common in different platforms. For example, virtual learners engage in peer learning and collaboration when they select VR (Su et al., 2024;), videos (Nguyen, 2024), AI (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023; Ericsson & Johansson, 2023), SNS (Le et al., 2024; Buddha et al., 2024; Kim & Kim, 2024) as the platforms through which they learn English. In line with Yunita et al. (2022), these platforms seem to facilitate interaction with other learners and teachers and enhance conversational skills. Self-regulated learning seems to be common in digital games (Acquah & Katz, 2020; Chowdhury et al., 2024; Kic-Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2024; Teng, 2024), e-learning (Teng & Wu, 2024; Meng et al., 2023), VR (Khafaga & Al-Johani, 2024), and AI (Chauncey & McKenna, 2023). Self-directed learning is mostly used in digital gaming platforms (Sözler, 2024; Zarrati et al., 2024), SNS (Ayesha & Qureshi, 2024; Le et al., 2024), e-learning (Mihai et al, 2022; Jabarali et al., 2024). Self-paced is mostly linked with videos (Abdallah & Alshaye, 2024), and finally multimodal literacies were related with e-learning (Li, 2020). It seems then there is no clear platform-related strategy as the activities presented by the different platforms are multifaceted, and therefore require the use of different strategies.

Figure 3: strategies and platforms

Main challenges and platforms

Many challenges have been reported relating to the different platforms (Figure 4). The challenges the learners face have been classified into technical, physical, psychological, pedagogical, and ethical.

Many challenges (6) have been identified with the e-learning platform. These challenges range from technical (Mihai et al., 2022) like lack of knowledge of handling e-learning resources and low network connectivity in remote regions (Jabarali et al., 2024), improper technology skills (Li, 2020); psychological like difficulty for the learners to motivate themselves while being isolated under stressful situations (Teng & Wu, 2024), increased anxiety and lack of enjoyment due to missing teacher and peer encouragement; pedagogical like improper topic selection (Li, 2020), and ethical like concerns about the platform's reliability and privacy (Meng et al., 2023).

With regards to digital gaming, the main challenges were technical limitations such as technological issues when applying technology due to a lack of skills and poor internet (Buddha et al., 2024; Chowdhury, et al., 2024), pedagogical whereby the gaming environments lack structured pedagogical materials (Teng, 2024; Zarrati et al., 2024), improper facilitation by teachers or institutions, or poor game choice (Acquah & Katz, 2020); physical like fatigue (Kic-Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2024), eye sight problems (Buddha et al., 2024), coping with Covid-19 related challenges (Sözler, 2024); and psychological, like lack of concentration and negative attitudes towards enjoyment (Kic-Drgas & Kılıçkaya, 2024).

Social networking sites come with four challenges. These include pedagogical issues like concerns about the amount and reliability of the information and materials (Le et al., 2024); informal styles of communication (Malik & Qureshi, 2024); psychological like learners' emotional and cognitive states (Budha et al., 2024) and addiction (Le et al., 2024); physical including eyesight damage (Le et al., 2024), and time constraints (Le et al., 2024).

Studies relating to Artificial Intelligence have identified four main challenges. These include technical problems like limited accessibility issues for the learners (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023), pedagogical like challenging assignment (Chauncey & McKenna, 2023), imperfect natural language understanding (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023); psychological like communication breakdown (Ericsson & Johansson, 2023), decrease in students' engagement and learning outcomes (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023), and inability to engage students with different affective characteristics (Nazari et al., 2021). Another challenge is ethical in nature, whereby racial, gender, and stereotypes-related algorithms generate discrimination and isolation for the learners (Zhai & Wibowo, 2023). Finally, cybersecurity and identity theft were revealed (Chauncey & McKenna, 2023).

Virtual reality comes with two main challenges. These count psychological obstacles like lack of student engagement and challenges to self-regulation (Su et al, 2024) and feeling anxious during virtual classes (Khafaga & Maneh AL-Johani, 2024), as well as technical challenges in using technology (Khafaga & Maneh AL-Johani, 2024; Su et al, 2024).

Finally, videos come with only one challenge. This challenge is mainly technical due to the learners' lack of exposure to technology-related concepts, the fast evolution of technological terminology, the technical complexity of jargon, and the obstacles they encounter when trying to integrate technology into language learning (Abdallah & Alshaye, 2024), and difficulty in the editing and uploading process (Nguyen, 2024).

Figure 4: Challenges and Platforms

As can be seen except for the SNS, the main challenge all the platforms have is technical. This can be explained by different reasons. SNS tend to have the fewest technical issues for learners of English thanks to their widespread use (Mushtaq et al., 2021), user-friendly design and ease of access (Seebaluck et al., 2015), and regular updates and maintenance that prevent technical issues (Sahebi & Formosa, 2022). Psychological issues also seem to be common in all the platforms except for the video. Lack of motivation or difficulty to concentrate seem to be common in e-learning, gaming, AI, and VR and increased anxiety emerges as a psychological issue in e-learning and AI. Ethical issues are common in e-learning, SNS, and AI. Pedagogical challenges seem to be issues in all the platforms except for VR and videos. The least cited challenges include physical issues and time constraints, which are common in digital games and SNS. It seems then that there is no specific platform-related challenge. The platforms had similar issues.

This part outlined the main findings relating to descriptive data and data relating to the four research questions. The next section will synthesize the main results and present some limitations that can be a springboard for future works.

Conclusions and recommendations

This paper reviewed a corpus of 23 papers spanning from January 2020 to May 2024 exploring English language learners' strategies, the digital learning platforms they use in their autonomous learning journey, and any platform-related strategies and challenges.

Results from descriptive data indicated a significant increase in the number of papers ($N=15$) during the first five months of 2024, and showed, therefore, a growing interest in exploring autonomous online learning that has been growing since the outbreak of the Covid-19. With regards to the methodologies used, by order of importance the quantitative method was mostly adopted (8 papers), showing the need for replication. This was followed by the review method (6 papers). The mixed method was used in 5 papers, and finally, the qualitative method was used in 4 papers.

Results pertaining to the four research questions, exploring the main adopted strategies, the different platforms, and any platform-related strategies and challenges yielded the following. With regards to the main strategies the autonomous learners adopted in their learning journey, the self-regulated strategies emerged as the most used one ($f=10$) involving metacognitive, self-efficacy, and meaning negotiation. This was followed by self-directed learning ($f=7$). Next come peer learning and collaboration strategies ($f=6$). Finally, self-paced and multimodal literacies learning ($f=1$), respectively, come as the least used strategies. As to the different learning online platforms, data revealed by order of frequency the digital games as the mostly used platforms ($f=7$), followed by e-learning ($f=6$), AI ($f=4$), SNS ($f=3$), then equally VR, and videos ($f=2$). To answer question three, no strategies-related platforms were revealed. The learners seemed to use strategies related to the activities provided by the platform in use. Finally, the platforms' challenges were several. The main challenge was technical which was common to all the platforms except SNS. Learners' psychological concerns were revealed with

e-learning, gaming, AI, VR, SNS platforms; including difficulty to motivate oneself, and increased anxiety. Pedagogical challenges emerged from e-learning, digital gaming, AI and SNS platforms due to for example, lack of structured educational materials, challenging assignments, and amount and reliability of the information and materials. Ethical challenges, like concerns about the platform's reliability and privacy seem to be common in e-learning and AI platforms. Physical challenges were mostly conspicuous with digital gaming and SNS. This was mainly due to fatigue and the likelihood of eye-sight damage due to long hours on these platforms. Finally, time constraints emerged with e-learning and SNS due to lack of time management by the learners. The challenges are not platform-related. All the platforms seemed to have common issues.

This piece of research outlines several theoretical gaps related mainly to the limited number of papers (23). The studies focusing on the benefits of these platforms for the learners' well-being were also lacking. Future research could extend the number of studied papers and consider conference and book contents in addition to journal papers. Finally, in addition to the examined learners' strategies in this paper, learners' preferred learning styles could also be examined in future works.

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